

THE ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF MILITARY SECURITY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article analyzes the conceptual essence, functions and principles of the concept of "military security" based on the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan and modern military-political theories.

Keywords. Military security, Defense Doctrine, military danger, military threat, hybrid wars, S. Huntington, objective civilian control, defense potential, National Security Council, strategic stability.

The rapid transformation of the global geopolitical architecture, the crisis of international legal institutions and the emergence of new military conflicts of a hybrid nature require every sovereign state to fundamentally reconsider its defense system. Military security is one of the fundamental pillars of national security, which is not only a guarantee of repelling external military aggression, but also of reliable protection of the internal stability and constitutional order from destructive factors. This article systematically analyzes the specific strategic approaches of the defense policy of New Uzbekistan, the dialectical balance between international law and military power, and the establishment of effective democratic (civilian) control over the armed forces.

In the defense doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concept of "military security" is briefly defined as "... the state of protection of national interests from threats to state security in the military sphere" [1].

From the definitions of military security, it is clear that all authors are based on the principle that military security is a state of protection of the state, society and the individual from destructive factors of a military nature. However, some of them called these factors - military danger, others - military threat. In our opinion, military danger and military threat are distinguished by a number of features in their nature.

Having considered the concept of "military security" and its essence, the following can be noted:

1. It is advisable that the essence of the concept of military security be fully reflected in regulatory documents.
2. Military security is an organizational part of the national security system, which means a state of sufficient protection of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state from military threats.
3. Military security involves a set of measures to protect the state, society and the individual from a whole range of internal and external military threats.
4. It is inappropriate to replace the term "military security" with the term "defense security", since ensuring military security includes not only the elimination of external military aggression, but also military threats of an internal nature (for example, terrorism, extremism, illegal changes to the constitutional order).

Thus, military security is defined as an important component of the national security system, which means the level of protection of the vital interests of an individual, society and the state from various forms of both external and internal military dangers and threats.

Based on the above considerations regarding security and this issue, the following should be noted:

- security is considered a scientific category, there are various interpretations of it, but the only principle that unites them is the state of protection from various threats and dangers;
- national security, which includes the protection of the interests and needs of the individual, society and the state, and as its components, social, political, economic, spiritual, cultural, military, environmental, information-psychological, resource security can be indicated;

- security in the country is ensured, implemented institutionally, in which the National Security Council under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan plays an important role;

- it is advisable to sufficiently study the National Security System of Uzbekistan within the framework of various disciplines and develop methods for improving this system.

An important part of military security is the system of ensuring military security, and under this concept it is necessary to understand the mechanism aimed at coordinating the activities of specific institutions, organizations, public associations and citizens within the framework of the current legislation, in accordance with the adopted strategy of the state in the field of military security. There are several doctrines on solving the problem of ensuring the country's military security, on the basis of which various approaches have been created.

The first approach is based on the concept of the primacy of the principles of international law in the military policy of the state, the essence of which is expressed in the fact that armed force as a guarantee of security and the unconditional implementation of international law norms should be replaced by broad-based cooperation and mutual trust [2].

The second approach to ensuring military security is force-based. In this regard, it is expressed in the desire to create and maintain a military capability adequate to existing or potential threats to national interests in peacetime. Being a supporter of the first approach to ensuring military security, Uzbekistan must at the same time take into account the current real situation in the world - the method of coercion, military threats and the fact that the direct use of force is not excluded from the means of achieving political goals by states in the near future. This situation gives rise to the only acceptable approach to ensuring military security for our country, that is, the third approach. The essence of the third approach is that, while recognizing the primacy of legal, diplomatic and other non-military means of eliminating wars, it is manifested in maintaining military force structures capable of ensuring a sufficient level of defense capability of the country [3]. Such a potential is understood as the possession of military power that, at minimal cost, in peacetime prevents a potential aggressor from starting a war, and in the event of military aggression, allows for strategic actions and the elimination of aggression. In other words, the armed forces of our country and other structures related to the defense system provide reliable protection of vital interests related to ensuring the independence and stability of our country, on the one hand.

The state takes the lead in implementing this third approach, which is based on:

- the stability of the primacy of international legal norms and principles that are organically interconnected and complement each other;

- accepts as partners all states that pursue a policy that does not harm the national interests and security of our country and does not contradict the Charter of the United Nations [4];

- expands mutual confidence-building measures in the military sphere, including the exchange of military information, defense doctrine, military construction, and coordination of military activity plans and measures.

Theoretically, the purpose of ensuring military security is to prevent, prevent the spread (localization) and eliminate (neutralization) of this military threat. Doctor of Military Sciences V. Zakharov and Candidate of Historical Sciences Kh. Mukhanbetkaliyev commented on this issue, writing, in particular: "In ensuring military security, the armed forces are assigned the task of suppressing forces as a strategy for intimidating a conditional opponent, the purpose of which is to prevent the outbreak of war" [5].

The strategic goal of ensuring military security is to form and maintain a political, international and military-strategic position that allows any state or alliance of states to weaken the role and significance of a potential rival country as a subject of international relations, to eliminate the possibility of various forms of influence aimed at changing the path of its socio-economic development, and to harm its national interests. Military security is achieved through the implementation of a single state policy in response to threats to the interests of the state, a system of measures of an economic, political, military, psychological, spiritual, cultural, scientific-technical, organizational and other nature.

Based on this, the activities of society and the state aimed at ensuring military security should be based on certain priority principles. In particular, the following can be indicated:

- the unity, interdependence and balance of all forms of security, the change in their priority depending on changes in the situation;
- the priority of political, economic and information means of ensuring military security;
- the subordination of the country's military security system and its parts to the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- the advancement of realistic tasks in terms of time, resources, forces and means;
- the implementation of the structure of the management of forces and means of ensuring military security in accordance with the distribution of powers of state authorities, its subjects and local government bodies.

Military security occupies an important place in the national security system and it is impossible to view it as a systemic category, as a single sector, at one level. It affects almost all spheres of society. Taking this into account, it can be noted that:

- military security is a holistic developing system, which has its own structure, inter-element and interrelationships with other systems (political, economic, social, technical, etc.);
- the military security system is an important component of national security, which in turn affects the military-political situation of the state, its internal and external security, and ensures its sovereignty, independence and territorial integrity.

The country's security system is formed on the basis of the interdependence and presence of such factors as social, economic, military-political, technological, scientific-technical, information-psychological, cultural, moral, and household. These are primarily aimed at solving socio-economic, socio-political, spiritual and moral problems and directing them towards the

goal. The formation of this system is a dual dialectical process, in which such laws as complexity, comprehensiveness and contradiction are reflected.

Military security has its own policy, and according to S. Huntington, there are three types of it, "namely:

- military security policy;
- internal security policy;
- situational security policy.

It can be shown that they operate at two levels of implementation: operational level and institutional level" [6]. "The security system, while being organizationally realistic, is aimed at solving problems in mutual interest, based on natural integration, on the basis of purposeful methods and means of civil society and state security. The role of the armed forces in this is of particular importance" [7]. In civil society, the armed forces do not lose their position, the scope of their tasks is improved, and the level of professionalism increases. This is due to the strengthening of citizen control over the armed forces, which is not an identification with democracy. After all, in a democratic society, the armed forces have great political power. S. Huntington, showing that civilian control is subjective and objective, noted that "under subjective control, the army is under the control of the interests of various political forces. Under objective control, the army is neutral and devoid of politics, subordinate to the state, and its autonomy is recognized by civil authorities" [8].

The main directions of ensuring military security can be outlined as follows:

- creation of favorable foreign policy conditions for ensuring the country's defense;
- clarification of priority national interests in the field of military security, a set of political-diplomatic and other non-military methods and means of ensuring it;
- implementation of military-political and strategic management over the country's defense, armed forces and other power structures;
- adoption of legislative acts in the field of defense, their improvement, creation of the economic and scientific and technical base necessary for the implementation of reliable defense;
- formation of a defense mindset among the country's population;
- maintenance of the armed forces and other power structures involved in defense in a high level of combat readiness, combat readiness and mobilization for armed defense of the country;
- development and strengthening of military science and military art;
- development of the defense industry complex.

All issues within the framework of military security problems should be resolved by a single body, that is, a system. This, in turn, will allow solving all problems arising within the framework of state security, from their occurrence to the complete elimination of their causes. In order to analyze potential threats, develop measures, methods and means to eliminate them, as well as directly eliminate emerging threats, the state will have a system that implements armed protection of its interests.

This system will be assigned the following probable tasks:

- identification and forecasting of external and internal threats to vital military security objects:

- implementation of a set of operational and long-term measures to prevent and eliminate threats;
- organization and maintenance of constant readiness of forces and means of ensuring military security;
- management of forces and means of ensuring military security in everyday conditions and emergency situations;
- ensuring the operation of military security facilities at the required level (meeting the need to ensure defense); participating in activities to ensure military security outside of it, based on national interests, on the basis of international agreements.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, the concept of ensuring military security is acquiring an absolutely new, strategic and balanced character.

The third approach chosen by Uzbekistan - the primacy of international law and the maintenance of a compact, modern and high-tech Armed Forces of the country, capable of repelling any aggression, relying on diplomatic means - is the most correct formula for the inviolability of our national sovereignty. In accordance with S. Huntington's principle of "objective civilian control", the authority of our national army as an institution free from politics, professional and unconditionally subject to state laws guarantees the stability of civil society.

Today, the consistent implementation of the tasks set out in our Defense Doctrine - digitization of the national defense industry, enrichment of military science with the latest achievements of artificial intelligence and asymmetric tactics, and raising patriotism and high defense thinking in society, primarily in the minds of young people, will serve to further strengthen the status of New Uzbekistan as a regional security center and an independent development subject.

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